

Changing Business Practices in Current Environment

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Abstract

As we all know that business is essential for the every part of economic growth to every village, city, town, municipality, corporation, state, national, international, unions and agents, etc. We may know that business can be classified into profit and non profit sectors. Whether profit or non profit sector it is essential to perform well for the welfare of the people. These days most of the people are doing the business for the money because money is so important also people are very aware about money. But the author says money alone is not good along with there should be some considerable ethical events must be taken place. Let us take a food industry, most of the food industry in the world they are using the chemicals for the preservation which all are not good for the health and which brings obesity, cancer, hypertension, cholesterol, blood pressure etc. The inorganic food deteriorating the human quality and may be the gene. Though the world is growing in medical sciences, but it is not necessary to invite all the troubles of our health. If the troubles are there it reduces the gene power of human beings and other beings and the productivity of the human's quality also will reduce it. So, it is totally against the nature.

Keywords: Business Practices and Current Environment.

Introduction

As we all know that business is essential for the every part of economic growth to every village, city, town, municipality, corporation, state, national, international, unions and agents, etc. We may know that business can be classified into profit and non-profit sectors. Whether profit or non-profit sector it is essential to perform well for the welfare of the people. These days most of the people are doing the business for the money because money is so important also people are very aware about money. But the author says money alone is not good along with there should be some considerable ethical events must be taken place. Let us take a food industry, most of the food industry in the world they are using the chemicals for the preservation which all are not good for the health and which brings obesity, cancer, hypertension, cholesterol, blood pressure etc. The inorganic food deteriorating the human quality and may be the gene. Though the world is growing in medical sciences, but it is not necessary to invite all the troubles of our health. If the troubles are there it reduces the gene power of human beings and other beings and the productivity of the human's quality also will reduce it. So, it is totally against the nature.

Now, let us take the following examples,

- In the agricultural sector, the scientists are modifying the gene for the high production to reduce the poverty. The gene modification and pesticides are not good for our health when we consume the product.
- Plastics industries are polluting the environment. It bring the air pollution which causes heart problem.
- Leather industry are polluting the river. Some leather products causes the skin diseases due to inorganic chemicals.
- Bio weapons are bringing the viruses which are very harm to the our human life.

- Nuclear business are killing each other.
- Medias are spoiling the people by showing unethical advertisements.
- Medicines are used by unnecessary steroid.
- Film industries are showing more about unlimited sexual feelings.
- Professional degrees are politicized.
- Mobile phones are causes cancers. Birds are dying and migrating to one place to another place.
- Businesses are done by only one particular group of people. That means one community which brings a lot of discriminations.

In the world there are around 220 countries. These countries can be classified into several ways. Some are, continent wise, developing world wise, developing country wise, income wise, intellectual wise, etc.

As we all know that countries can also be classified into no, low, middle and high income countries. No and low income countries might have a lot of poverty, marginalizes and deprived community people. Their salaries and wages are very less than the cost of the living. When they buy some product their product will be either cheated or cannot be used may be more than a few days. It is not only happening for the products also services. In this case, the income which spent by the poor even it is not meeting their requirements. Either it is cheated or threatend end. Such kind of business also must be concentrated to improve the quality of poor people.

Pesticides, chemicals, pollution, wrong information in the media, etc are another issues of the business. It must be rectified it. Else they all bring problem to the health of us and it will mislead us.

Some unorganized sectors also making the people into poverty. It is called poverty motivation. Example, religions groups make the people not to work and not to think rationally which are all making the people into poverty.

When I am traveling the world I found who consumes a natural related products that is organic food and living naturally and improvement of their life is far better than the artificial life.

Conclusion

Everyone and every country is important of each other. Everyone is working towards the world development but we have to keep in our mind that we have to do a good and important business for the human development. If it is not going into the correct direction it will hard to our human life not only for this generation but also the future generation. People are in unnecessary status and ego but not good business for our good environment. In this paper, the author mentioned about negative points of the business because it is the duty of the author to identify problems in the business areas to improve the business environment in the current scenario.

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